

Concentration fluctuations in binary molten alloys

V. N. Singh, L. C. Prasad[#] and M. Jha^{*}

University Department of Chemistry, T. M. Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812 007, India

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In view of the importance of concentration fluctuation in the long wavelength limit in the study of alloying behaviour of molten alloys, an attempt has been made to obtain expressions for $S_{CC}(o)$ from two different theories, i.e. quasi-lattice theory and electronic theory based on hard sphere model. The expression for $S_{CC}(o)$ from hard sphere model involves additive hard sphere diameter and non-additive potential depth. The above expression for $S_{CC}(o)$ has been utilised to investigate the alloying behaviour of Na-K molten alloys. Both the theories suggest occurrence of like atoms pairing (self-coordination), leading to segregation in Na-K molten alloys. The role of non-additivity of potential depth on $S_{CC}(o)$ has also been investigated with reference to Na-K system.

To understand the mixing behaviour of two elemental metals forming a binary alloy has been a subject of interest as it reveals¹⁻⁴ the energetics and structural readjustment of the constituent atoms. Considerable progress¹⁻⁶ has been made to understand the energetics of binary alloys by using two distinct theories, viz. statistical mechanical theory and electronic theory of mixing. Two opposite phenomena, i.e. the formation of intermetallic compounds and phase separation, are being investigated through the understanding of the energetics⁷⁻¹⁰ of liquid alloys. Heterocoordination (unlike-atoms pairing as nearest neighbours) is the measure of chemical order in the alloy, leading to the formation of intermetallic compounds, whereas phase separation or segregation is related to the self coordination (like-atoms pairing as nearest neighbours).

Recently, Bhatia and Thornton¹¹ partial structure factors in the long wavelength limit have attracted much more attention of theoreticians as well as of experimentalists, to understand alloying behaviour¹²⁻¹⁷ of liquid alloys. Of all concentration fluctuations in the long wavelength limit, $S_{CC}(o)$ has emerged as one of the most important and powerful microscopic functions to understand the nature of interatomic interactions. The phenomena of ordering and segregation can be easily understood by $S_{CC}(o)$. It is also being used to analyse the factors responsible for the formation of metallic glasses¹⁸, which are obtained by quenching the molten alloys. Many other properties^{3,5,19,20}, such as diffusion, viscosity, surface tension etc. can also be explained with the knowledge of $S_{CC}(o)$. Recently, Osman and Singh²¹ have utilised Lennard-Jones potential to explain the stability of Ne-Ar mixture through the study of $S_{CC}(o)$. On the other hand, Biben and Hansen⁸ also obtained expression for $S_{CC}(o)$ under the framework of Percus-Yevic

(PY) approximation. The effect of non-additivity of hard sphere diameter is also being investigated to understand the problem of phase separation and compound formation. Keeping in mind the importance of $S_{CC}(o)$, an attempt has been made to understand the alloying behaviour of Na-K molten alloys through the study of $S_{CC}(o)$ by using two different approaches, viz. quasi-lattice theory and the hard sphere model. In quasi-lattice model the energy parameter comes through order energy while hard sphere model involves potential depth. The effect of non-additivity of the potential has also been explored with reference to Na-K system.

Partial structure factors of binary molten alloys : Using weak scattering approximations and Vanhove²² correlation technique, Bhatia and Thornton¹¹ established a relation between the coherent intensity per atom, $I(q)$, and partial structure factors^{23,24}, $S_{ij}(q)$ ($i, j = N, C$), of binary alloy, AB, consisting of A and B atoms, which is given as

$$I(q) = \langle b \rangle^2 S_{NN}(q) + (\Delta b)^2 S_{CC}(q) + 2\langle \Delta b \rangle S_{NC}(q) \quad (1)$$

where

$$\langle b \rangle = C_A b_A + C_B b_B \text{ and } \Delta b = b_A - b_B$$

b_A and b_B denote coherent scattering amplitudes of A and B components respectively. $C_A (=N_A/N)$ and $C_B (=N_B/N)$ are concentrations of A and B atoms respectively; N_i ($i = A, B$) refers to the number of i -th atom in such a way that total number of atoms, N , becomes equal to $\sum N_i$.

Partial structure factors in the long wavelength limit : In the long wavelength limit ($q \rightarrow 0$), the structure factors become more physically significant. These have the property that at temperature above Debye temperature and in the long wavelength limit, $S_{NN}(o)$ and $S_{CC}(o)$ represent respec-

[#]Present address : Inst. fur Anorganisch Chemie, Universitat Wien, WähringerstraBe 42, A-1090, Vienna, Austria.

tively, the mean thermal fluctuations in the number of particles and in the concentration in given volume. The correlation between these two fluctuations is represented by S_{NC} (o). These are expressed¹¹ as

$$S_{NN}(o) = (N/V) K_B T \chi_T + \delta^2 S_{CC}(o) \quad (2)$$

$$S_{NC}(o) = -\delta S_{CC}(o) \quad (3)$$

$$S_{CC}(o) = NK_B T [(\partial^2 G_M)/(\partial C_{T,P,N}^2)]^{-1} \quad (4)$$

where χ_T is the isothermal compressibility, G_M the Gibb's free energy of mixing, $\delta [(1/V) (\partial V/\partial C)_{T,P,N}]$ is the dilatation factor and K_B refers to Boltzmann's factor. $S_{CC}(o)$ can also be expressed in terms of activity a_i , ($i = A, B$), as

$$S_{CC}(o) = C_B a_A [\partial a_A / \partial C_A]_{T,P,N}^{-1} \quad (5a)$$

$$S_{CC}(o) = C_A a_B [\partial a_B / \partial C_B]_{T,P,N}^{-1} \quad (5b)$$

An expression for $S_{CC}(o)$ may be easily developed from proper analytical expression for G_M or activity. Once $S_{CC}(o)$ is known, other structure factors, i.e. $S_{NN}(o)$ and $S_{NC}(o)$ etc. follow readily.

Quasi-lattice model :

Basic assumptions of the model and free energy of mixing of binary molten alloys : The free energy of mixing (G_M) of binary molten alloys at a constant temperature is related to entropy of mixing (S_M) and enthalpy of mixing (H_M) through standard thermodynamic relations,

$$G_M = H_M - TS_M \quad (6)$$

It is clear from the above relation that free energy of mixing is influenced by two factors, namely, the entropic (due to S_M) and the enthalpic (due to H_M) effects. H_M is the term which contains the energy parameter while S_M is the measure of disorder present in the alloy in the absence of energetic effect. For probing the effect of both factors, H_M and S_M have been dealt separately. The effect of both the factors has been obtained through the study of G_M .

Under the framework of quasi-lattice model²⁵, it is simple to assume that the number of lattice sites occupied by the constituent atoms might depend on the size of the atoms. On the basis of the above assumptions, the bigger atom B of the alloy, AB, is supposed to occupy r lattice sites, whereas smaller constituent atom A occupies one lattice site. As the total number of lattice sites is just N , which is given as

$$N = N_A + rN_B \quad (7)$$

r may be approximated as

$$r = \Omega_B / \Omega_A \quad (8)$$

where Ω_A and Ω_B are atomic volumes of A and B atoms of the alloy. Following Guggenheim²⁵, number of nearest pairs has been denoted by Zq , where q is related to r by the relation,

$$(1/2)Z(r - q) = (r - 1) \quad (9)$$

If N_{ij} ($i, j = A, B$) be the number of contacts between i and j atoms and ϵ_{ij} be the bond energy of i, j ($i, j = A, B$) atoms, then configurational energy, E , becomes

$$E = N_{AA} \epsilon_{AA} + N_{BB} \epsilon_{BB} + N_{AB} \epsilon_{AB} \quad (10)$$

The configurational partition function, Q , is related to configurational energy through the relation,

$$Q = \sum_E g \exp(-E/K_B T) \quad (11)$$

where g , often called the degree of degeneracy, specifies the number of possible arrangements of the atoms on the lattice.

Q has been solved²⁵ to obtain separate expressions for S_M and H_M from equation (6). When $H_M = 0$, the entropy of mixing S_M becomes equal to

$$\begin{aligned} G_M / NK_B T = -S_M / NK_B T = & C_A \ln [C_A / (C_A + rC_B)] \\ & + C_B \ln [rC_B / (C_A + rC_B)] \\ & - 1/2 Z C_A \ln [(C_A + qC_B) / (C_A + rC_B)] \\ & - 1/2 Z q C_B \ln [(C_A + qC_B) r / \\ & (C_A + rC_B) q] \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The above equation simplifies considerably for $Z \rightarrow \infty$, as :

$$G_M / NK_B T = -S_M / NK_B T = C_A \ln \phi + C_B \ln (1 - \phi) \quad (13)$$

where $\phi = C_A / (C_A + rC_B)$.

For $H_M \neq 0$, we get from quasi lattice theory²⁵,

$$H_M / NK_B T = [qC_A C_B / (C_A + qC_B)] W / K_B T \quad (14)$$

where $W = Z [\epsilon_{AB} - (\epsilon_{AA} + \epsilon_{BB})/2]$ is the order energy. Obviously $W < 0$ corresponds to heterocoordination, while for $W > 0$, like atoms pairing, i.e. self-coordination occurs. If there is no preferential bonding of any type in the mixture, W becomes zero indicating the ideal case. For $Z \rightarrow \infty$,

$$(r - q) / r \rightarrow 0 \quad (15)$$

and equation (14) reduces to

$$H_M / NK_B T = C_A (1 - \phi) W / K_B T \quad (16)$$

By combining equations (13) and (16), we obtain an expression for free energy of mixing G_M , containing both

enthalpic and entropic contributions,

$$G_M/NK_B T = C_A \ln \phi + C_B \ln (1 - \phi) + \frac{C_A (1 - \phi) W/K_B T}{C_A + r C_B} \quad (17)$$

Concentration fluctuations in the long wavelength limit : In the absence of energetic effect, i.e. $H_M = 0$, we have used equations (4) and (13) to obtain an expression for $S_{CC}(0)$. From equation (4), we get $S_{CC}(0)$ as

$$S_{CC}(0) = C_A C_B / [1 + C_A C_B \{(r-1)/(C_A + r C_B)\}^2] \quad (18)$$

For $r = 1$, ($\Omega_A \equiv \Omega_B$) the above equation reduces to the ideal case,

$$S_{CC}(0, id) = C_A C_B \quad (19)$$

In order to obtain expression for $S_{CC}(0)$ containing both the contributions, namely, entropic and enthalpic, we have used equations (17) and (4),

$$S_{CC}(0) = C_A C_B / [1 - C_A C_B f(c)] \quad (20)$$

$$\text{where } f(c) = [C_A (r-1)^3 + 2r^2 (W/K_B T) - r(r-1)^2] / (C_A + r C_B)^3 \quad (21)$$

In the absence of enthalpic effect ($H_M = 0$), the above equation reduces to equation (18). When $r = 1$, equation (20) becomes

$$S_{CC}(0) = C_A C_B / (1 - C_A C_B 2W/K_B T) \quad (22)$$

when $W/K_B T = 0$, $S_{CC}(0)$ is given by equation (19), indicating the ideal case.

Hard sphere model and $S_{CC}(0)$:

As assumed earlier, binary alloy, AB, contains N atoms in volume Ω , of which $N_A (\equiv N C_A)$ is the number of A atoms and $N_B (\equiv N C_B)$ is the number of B atoms. σ_{AA} and σ_{BB} are hard sphere diameters of A and B atoms respectively. As earlier, B atom is supposed to be bigger than that of A ($\sigma_{BB} > \sigma_{AA}$). The total density, ρ , and packing fraction, η , of the above system may be given as

$$\rho = N/\Omega \quad (23)$$

$$\eta = (\pi/6) \rho (C_A \sigma_{AA}^3 + C_B \sigma_{BB}^3) \quad (24)$$

In order to obtain analytical expression for $S_{CC}(0)$, it is assumed that constituent atoms of the binary alloy AB are interacting with Lennard-Jones potential, i.e.

$$\phi_{ij} \equiv \phi_{ij}^{LJ} = 4 \varepsilon_{ij} [(\sigma_{ij}/r)^{12} - (\sigma_{ij}/r)^6] \quad (25)$$

where ε_{ij} ($i, j = A, B$) are the attractive potential depths.

Here in our theoretical model we have considered hard sphere diameter as additive ($\sigma_{AB} = (\sigma_{AA} + \sigma_{BB})/2$). As regards potential depth, it has been treated as non-additive. For this we have introduced interactive energy parameter α to express ε_{AB} as

$$\varepsilon_{AB} = \alpha (\varepsilon_{AA} \varepsilon_{BB})^{1/2} \quad (26)$$

when $\alpha = 1$, ε_{AB} becomes equal to $(\varepsilon_{AA} \varepsilon_{BB})^{1/2}$ as used in general practice. On the basis of WCA perturbation theory^{26,27}, the above L-J potential has been divided into reference part under the hard sphere approximation as $\phi_{ij}^{HS}(r)$ and tail part as $\phi_{ij}^T(r)$ which contain long range attractive contributions, i.e.

$$\phi_{ij}(r) = \phi_{ij}^{HS}(r) + \phi_{ij}^T(r) \quad (i, j = A, B) \quad (27)$$

Under the framework of random phase approximation (RPA)²⁸, the Helmholtz free energy, F , and pressure, P , of the system may be expressed as

$$F = F_{HS} + (1/2) \rho \sum C_i C_j \bar{\phi}_{ij}^T(0) \quad (28)$$

$$P = P_{HS} + (1/2) \rho^2 \sum C_i C_j \bar{\phi}_{ij}^T(0) \quad (29)$$

where

$$\bar{\phi}_{ij}^T(0) = 4\pi \int_0^\infty r^2 dr \phi_{ij}^T(r) \quad (30)$$

Gibbs free energy G becomes

$$G = F + P/\rho = G_{HS} + G_T \quad (31)$$

where

$$G_{HS} = F_{HS} + P_{HS}/\rho \quad (32)$$

$$G_T = \rho \sum_{ij} C_i C_j \bar{\phi}_{ij}^T(0) \quad (33)$$

Equation (27), when handled under WCA theory, gives reference potential, $\phi_{ij}^R(r)$ and tail potential $\phi_{ij}^T(r)$ as

$$\phi_{ij}^R(r) = \phi_{ij}^L(r) + \varepsilon_{ij}, \quad r \leq r_{ij}^{\min} \\ = 0, \quad r \geq r_{ij}^{\min} \quad (34)$$

$$\phi_{ij}^T(r) \approx -\varepsilon_{ij}, \quad r \leq r_{ij}^{\min} \\ = \phi_{ij}^{LJ}(r), \quad r \geq r_{ij}^{\min} \quad (35)$$

with

$$r_{ij}^{\min} = (2)^{1/6} \sigma_{ij}$$

$\phi_{ij}^R(r)$ has been approximated to be equal to hard sphere

potential $\phi_{ij}^{HS}(r)$. Here the expressions for F_{HS} and P_{HS} obtained under the PY approximation have been utilised, which are given as

$$F_{HS} = \sum_i C_i \mu_i^{HS} + P_{HS} / \rho \quad (36)$$

The chemical potential, μ_i^{HS} , and the pressure, P_{HS} ($i, j = A, B$), are expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_i / K_B T = & \ln [\rho_i (2\pi h^2 / m_i K_B T^{3/2})] - \ln [1 - \eta] \\ & + 3Z\sigma_{ij} / (1 - \eta) + (3\sigma_{ij}^2 / 2) [(3Z^2 / (1 - \eta)^2) - 2\gamma / \\ & (1 - \eta)] + (\pi/6) \sigma_{ij}^3 P_{HS} / K_B T \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

$$\begin{aligned} P_{HS} / K_B T = & \rho (1 + \eta + \eta^2) / (1 - \eta)^3 + [-\pi\rho_A\rho_B \\ & (\sigma_{BB} - \sigma_{AA})^2 (\sigma_{AB} + (1/2) \sigma_{AB} \sigma_{BB} Z) / (1 - \eta)^3 \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

where

$$Y = (\pi/6)\rho [C_A \sigma_{AA} + C_B \sigma_{BB}] \quad (39)$$

$$Z = (\pi/6)\rho [C_A \sigma_{AA}^2 + C_B \sigma_{BB}^2] \quad (40)$$

Under the present model, equation (5) divides $S_{CC}(o)$ into two parts, i.e.

$$S_{CC}(o)^{-1} = S_{CC}^{HS}(o)^{-1} + S_{CC}^T(o)^{-1} \quad (41)$$

It is simple to obtain expression for $S_{CC}(o)$ if one has suitable expression for hard sphere and tail contributions. By using equation from (37) to (41), we obtain $S_{CC}(o)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} S_{CC}^{HS}(o)^{-1} = & (C_A C_B)^{-1} + (\pi\rho/2) [9Z^3 D_3^2 / (1 - \eta)^4 \\ & + (18Z^2 D_2 D_3 + 4YZD_3^2) / (1 - \eta)^3 + \{9ZD_2^2 \\ & + 4YD_1 D_2 + 4ZD_1 D_3 + (\pi\rho/18) D_3^2\} / (1 - \eta)^2 \\ & + 4D_1 D_2 / (1 - \eta)] \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} S_{CC}^T(o)^{-1} = & (\rho K / K_B T) [(C - \eta)(Q_1 + Q_2) - (\pi\rho D_3/3) \\ & (C_A Q_1 + C_B Q_2)] \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} D_1 = & \sigma_{AA} - \sigma_{BB} \\ D_2 = & \sigma_{AA}^2 - \sigma_{BB}^2 \\ D_3 = & \sigma_{AA}^3 - \sigma_{BB}^3 \\ Q_1 = & \varepsilon_{AA} \sigma_{AA}^3 - \varepsilon_{AB} \sigma_{AB}^3 \\ Q_2 = & \varepsilon_{BB} \sigma_{BB}^3 - \varepsilon_{AB} \sigma_{AB}^3 \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

Following equation (41), $S_{CC}(o)^{-1}$ is obtained by adding equations (42) and (43) with the constant K obtained from equation (30) over the reduced interatomic separation, r^* ,

$$K = 4\pi \int_0^\alpha dr^* r^{*2} \phi_{AA}^T(r^*) \quad (45)$$

with

$$r^* = r / \sigma_{AA}$$

Here in our model, we have taken additive hard sphere and non-additive potential depth. It is interesting to see that when the hard sphere diameter (σ_{ij}) and the potential depth (ε_{ij}) of the constituent atoms of the binary mixture are equal, i.e.

$$\sigma_{AA} = \sigma_{BB} = \sigma_{AB} \text{ and } \varepsilon_{AA} = \varepsilon_{BB} = \varepsilon_{AB}, \text{ i.e. } \alpha = 1$$

the other terms (eq. 46) vanish

$$D_1 = D_2 = D_3 = 0$$

and

$$Q_1 = Q_2 = 0$$

In this case, equations (42) and (43) reduce to $(C_A C_B)^{-1}$ and zero respectively.

$$S_{CC}^{HS}(o) = C_A C_B$$

$$S_{CC}^T(o) = 0$$

and

$$S_{CC}(o) = S_{CC}(o, id) = C_A C_B$$

This is the case for ideal mixing.

Results and Discussion

For elucidation, we have chosen Na-K molten alloys. Equation (20), which is based on quasi-lattice model, has been utilised to compute $S_{CC}(o)$ as a function of concentration. The basic inputs for the computation are the ratio, r , of atomic volumes and order potential, W . The atomic volumes of pure Na and K have been taken from Smithells reference book. In principle, W can be calculated from first principles by using pairwise interaction of pseudopotential method^{29,30}, but little work has been done in this direction. Following Prasad and Singh¹⁵⁻¹⁷, we have calculated order potential, W , from the observed activity or from the free energy of mixing data at equi-atomic composition.

$$W / K_B T = 0.9932; \Omega_{Na} = 520.03599 \text{ a.u.};$$

$$\Omega_K = 269.13704 \text{ a.u.}$$

The computed values of $S_{CC}(o)$ of Na-K system at 384 K have been plotted in Fig. 1 as a function of concentration. Since the experimental determination of $S_{CC}(o)$ has not been accomplished successfully, the $S_{CC}(o)$, computed from mea-

Fig. 1. Concentration fluctuations ($q \rightarrow 0$), $S_{CC}(o)$ of Na-K molten alloys at 384 K : (x) experimental³¹, (□) quasi-lattice theory, (Δ) hard sphere model with $K = 11.65$, (o) hard sphere model with K from equation (47), (—) ideal values.

sured activity data following the equalities of equation (5), is taken as the experimental one, which is widely accepted. With a view to minimising the errors involved in numerical differentiation, we have made the series-expansion of observed activity data and then have evaluated $(\partial a_A / \partial \chi_A)$. The experimental values³¹ along with ideal values are also given in Fig. 1. The computed values of $S_{CC}(o)$ from theory (equation 20) and experimental values are in good agreement. $S_{CC}(o)$ is greater than the ideal values, $S_{CC}(o, id)$, at all concentrations. A slight deviation in the magnitude is observed in the concentration range, $0.2 \leq C_{Na} \leq 0.4$. This is the indication of the existence of self-coordination leading to the segregation.

On the other hand, expressions for $S_{CC}(o)$, (equations 42 and 43), obtained from hard sphere model have been utilised to compute $S_{CC}(o)$ as a function of concentration. The required inputs for above computation are hard sphere diameter (σ_{Na-Na} and σ_{K-K}), density (ρ) and potential depths (ϵ_{Na-Na} and ϵ_{K-K}). Hard sphere diameter is usually determined from observed entropy or by minimising the interatomic potential or by fitting the first peak of observed static structure factor. In view of the diversity of the result, we have determined σ_{ij} , by minimising the Helmholtz free energy, i.e.

$$(\partial F / \partial \sigma_{ij})_{\Omega, T} = 0$$

It is simple to determine ϵ_{ij} from the knowledge of pair potential. The observed atomic volumes of the pure components (Na and K) have been utilised to compute the volume

of the alloy at different concentrations by using the value of experimental volume change. The knowledge of volume of the alloy gives us density (ρ) and packing fraction, η , (equations 23 and 24). Above parameters used for the evaluation of $S_{CC}(o)$ of Na-K system are

$$\sigma_{Na-Na} = 6.2222 \text{ a.u.}; \sigma_{K-K} = 7.5999 \text{ a.u.};$$

$$\epsilon_{Na-Na} = -9.080619 \times 10^{-4} \text{ a.u.}; \epsilon_{K-K} = -10.50368 \times 10^{-4} \text{ a.u.}$$

The constant K appearing in equation (43) has been calculated following equation (47). Since both the size ratio ($\sigma_{BB} / \sigma_{AA}$) and the ratio of potential depth ($\epsilon_{BB} / \epsilon_{AA}$) contribute to $S_{CC}(o)$ (equations 42 and 43), the interaction parameter, α , has been treated as a parameter. $S_{CC}(o)$ for Na-K system was calculated with K obtained from equation (45) for different values of α , say $\alpha > 1$ and $\alpha < 1$. It is observed that $S_{CC}(o)$ is smaller than the ideal values for all values of α , i.e. α does not significantly affect $S_{CC}(o)$. Because of this we took $\alpha = 0.18$, a smaller value and computed $S_{CC}(o)$ as a function of concentration, which is depicted in Fig. 1.

As stated above, $S_{CC}(o)$ is always smaller than the ideal values indicating the pairing of unlike atoms as nearest neighbours. The result (heterocoordination) is contrary to the experimental findings and quasi-lattice theory results. This might be happening due to the larger values of the ratio of hard sphere diameter (σ_K / σ_{Na}). In order to explain Na-K system from hard sphere model, we treated K as a parameter and fixed K at 11.65. For this value of K and same $\alpha = 0.18$, $S_{CC}(o)$ was computed, which are plotted in the same figure. It is interesting to observe that at all concentrations, $S_{CC}(o)$ is greater than the ideal values, i.e. $S_{CC}(o, id)$. Our theoretical expressions obtained from both models explain the phenomenon of self-coordination in Na-K system to a great extent. In Na-K system, self-coordination, i.e. pairing of like atoms as nearest neighbours (Na-Na and K-K) occurs. It is also observed that the magnitude of $S_{CC}(o)$ in both cases differ from experimental values. The extent of segregation also differs in both approaches.

In order to investigate the role of interaction parameter, α , we have also computed $S_{CC}(o)$ for different values of α . In the above calculations, K and other parameters are the same as above. The results are given in Fig. 2. The extent of segregation has been found to be decreasing with the increasing value of α . For $\alpha > .19$, atomic order exists at all concentrations in Na-K melt. It will be proper to mention that, for $\alpha = 1$, the system does not behave ideally. It happens because of larger size-mismatch $\sigma_K > \sigma_{Na}$ and bigger values for potential depth (ϵ_{K-K} , ϵ_{Na-Na}). As discussed earlier, for $\alpha = 1$, $\sigma_{AA} = \sigma_{BB} = \sigma_{AB}$ and $\epsilon_{AA} = \epsilon_{BB} = \epsilon_{AB}$, $S_{CC}(o)$ reduces to the ideal case.

Fig. 2. $S_{CC}(0)$ of Na-K system at 384 K with $K = 11.65$, for different values of interaction energy parameter, α : (\square) $\alpha = 1.2$, (\diamond) $\alpha = 1.0$, (Δ) $\alpha = 0.8$, (\times) $\alpha = 0.6$, ($*$) $\alpha = 0.4$, (\circ) $\alpha = \text{ideal}$, (—) $\alpha = 0.18$.

Conclusion : The phenomena of segregation and order have been discussed in the framework of two distinct theories, namely, quasi-lattice model and hard sphere model. Analytical expression for $S_{CC}(0)$ obtained from both models have been utilised to understand the alloying behaviour of Na-K molten alloys. Both the quasi-lattice theory and the hard sphere model explain the phenomenon of segregation in Na-K system successfully. The effect of interacting parameter, α , has also been investigated with reference to the above system. Our theoretical results suggest that the segregation not only depends upon α but also upon K . Since our expressions from hard sphere model, which involves K , is derived by using Lennard-Jones potential, the value of K might be one of the responsible factors in the mixing of alloy. We are trying to improve our expression by using other expressions for potential. While investigating the effect of α on the mixing, it is also observed that size-mismatch and larger value of potential depth influence the phase separation and compound formation to a great extent.

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